

Securely Storing Searchable String in Database

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Abstract—Privacy and security of users data is an important concept involved in storing user information in a database. This paper discusses on how to securely store searchable string data in a database using standard encryption and hashing techniques. This method of storing string values in database prevent rainbow table attack .

Keywords—PBKDF2,SHA-2,AES

I. INTRODUCTION (THE PROBLEM)

Storing user data on the server has always been a chore. Consider the following scenario: someone obtains access to our database. Only way to prevent them from reading sensitive information about users is to encrypt data.

But by encrypting data using symmetric encryption we need a way to save the symmetric key in the server. Saving key in database or in server file is also a risk, if the attacker gains access to server, then all the data encrypted using that key is also at risk.

Encryption increases security but we cannot perform database queries to perform search. We cannot ensure indexing on the encrypted data.

II. USING PASSWORD BASED KEY DERIVATION FUNCTION

We can make use of algorithms such as PBKDF2(Password-Based Key Derivation Function 1 and 2. By using this algorithm we can generate keys based on the input string. So in the scenario of passwords the key generated will be always equal. This will slow down the password cracking tools. As a result, guess rates dropped from hundreds of thousands to a few tens of thousands per second.

PBKDF2 works by "stretching" strings, which means it takes the password (or any string) you provide it and executes hundreds of intricate changes on it until it creates a sequence of bytes of any length you choose, with no obvious resemblance to the original text.

Because the password is not saved anywhere, you must enter it each time you start your web server; it will use the password to generate the encryption key and then utilise that key without storing it.

III. BLIND INDEXING

The creation of blind indexes overcomes the second issue. The goal is to hash the search phrases and then index the resulting hash.

For example, assume we wish to know which (encrypted) fields include the word 'mango'.To begin, we construct a hash from the word:'mango' -> 14231297424532579. Then, without retaining the actual word 'mango,' we generate an index that lists all the fields that have the hash 12481991424532578.

The hash 12481991424532578 appears in rows 34, 156,

1240, and this is referred to as a "blind index" since it does not actually hold the word "mango," therefore an attacker who obtains the database will be unable to determine which words are contained on which fields based on that index.

Finally, if we need to discover rows containing the word "mango," we compute its hash (the number 12481991424532578), then look it up in the blind index.

To make this work, we'll need a hashing algorithm. We can use the same string stretching approach (PBKDF2) that we used to extract the key from the password: Simply extending the word into a 6-byte string (6 being the maximum number of bytes supported by the crypto library to convert to an integer), we can then interpret that string as an integer that we can use as the hash..

We may increase the level of security by producing the hash with a secret salt - and producing that hash using the same password we used to generate the key. Using a dictionary attack, the attacker will be unable to tell which word is hashed to 12481991424532578 without knowing the password.

IV. ALGORITHM

A. STORING SECRET

STEP1 : Key Generation

- Stretches the password in order to produce an encryption key K.

STEP 2 : Encryption

- Encrypts data using the key K created in the previous step.

STEP 3: Hash generation

- Use the salt we created from the password to compute a unique integer hash from the provided message.

STEP 4: Index creation

- Create an index for the message using the hash

computed in the previous step.

B. SEARCHING

STEP1 : Key Generation

- Stretches the password in order to produce an encryption key K.

STEP 2: Hash generation

- Use the salt we created from the password to compute a unique integer hash from the provided message.

STEP 4: Searching

- Perform search in the database for the hash digest generated in the previous step.

V. CONCLUSION

Security is a moving target, we should take into consideration all the ways we can protect the data.

Information with high priority should be saved in a database always encrypted and information such as passwords should be saved by using secure hashing algorithms, and we have seen a way to make such information searchable using a combination of hashing and encryption algorithms.

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